

TIME4CS

SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTIONAL CHANGES TO
PROMOTE CITIZEN SCIENCE IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

D4.4: Report on all Workshops

Gitte Kragh (AU) | 29/06/2023

Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen (AU) | 29/06/2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006201

Work Package	WP4
Task	T4.2
Due Date	30/06/2023
Submission Date	30/06/2023
Author(s)	Gitte Kragh (AU), Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen (AU)
Contributor(s)	Marta Solis Mateos (CRG)
Reviewer(s)	Claudia Iasillo (APRE), Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)
Version	1.0
Dissemination Level	Public
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.8083037

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	20/06/2023	First draft of the document	Gitte Kragh (AU), Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen (AU)
0.2	26/06/2023	Comments from partners	Claudia Iasillo (APRE), Alessio Livio Spera (APRE), Marta Solis Mateos (CRG)
1.0	30/06/2023	Final version of the document	Gitte Kragh (AU), Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen (AU)

Disclaimer: The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 ABOUT THIS DELIVERABLE	8
2. DEVELOPMENT AND PLANNING OF TRAINING DAYS AND WORKSHOPS	8
2.1 COORDINATION WITH RELATED ACTIVITIES	8
2.2 OVERALL PREPARATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF WORKSHOPS.....	9
2.3 DOCUMENTATION AND EVALUATION	10
3. TRAINING DAYS AND WORKSHOPS.....	11
3.1 TRAIN-THE-TRAINER WORKSHOP, BRUSSELS, 13 DECEMBER 2022	11
3.2 TRAINING DAY KTU, 13 MARCH 2023	13
3.2.1 <i>WS1: Policy and Assessment Workshop</i>	13
3.2.2 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	14
3.2.3 <i>WS2: Citizen Science Workshop</i>	15
3.2.3 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	16
3.3 TRAINING DAY TYNDALL, 28 MARCH 2023.....	17
3.3.1 <i>WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact</i>	17
3.3.2 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	18
3.3.3 <i>WS2: Assessing the impacts of citizen science</i>	19
3.3.4 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	20
3.4 TRAINING DAY CRG, 8 MAY 2023.....	21
3.4.1 <i>WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact</i>	21
3.4.2 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	22
3.4.3 <i>WS2: Citizen science in research project proposals</i>	23
3.4.4 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	24
3.5 TRAINING DAY UNISR, 19 MAY 2023	26
3.5.1 <i>WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact</i>	26
3.5.2 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	26
3.5.3 <i>WS2: Citizen Science Methodologies & Communication</i>	27
3.5.4 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	28
3.5.5 <i>WS3: Train-the-Trainer</i>	29
3.5.6 <i>Evaluation and general observations</i>	30
4. CONCLUSIONS	33
APPENDIX A.....	34
A.1 KTU TRAINING DAY	34
A.1.1 <i>Training Day Agenda</i>	34
A.2 TYNDALL TRAINING DAY	34
A.2.1 <i>Training Day Agenda</i>	34
A.3 CRG TRAINING DAY	34
A.3.1 <i>Training Day Agenda</i>	34
A.4 UNISR TRAINING DAY.....	35
A.4.1 <i>Training Day Agenda</i>	35

Table of Figures

Figure 1. Target Evaluation. Example from UniSR workshop for Researchers, 19 May 2023.....	10
Figure 2. Agenda for the Train-the-Trainer workshop for consortium members, Brussels, 13 Dec. 2023	12
Figure 3. Agenda for policy & assessment workshop at KTU, 13 March 2023.....	13
Figure 4. Evaluation targets from WS1 at KTU.....	15
Figure 5. Agenda for second training workshop at KTU, 13 March 2023.....	16
Figure 6. Evaluation targets from WS2 at KTU.....	17
Figure 7. Agenda for the impact and funding workshop at Tyndall, 28 March 2023.....	18
Figure 8. Evaluation targets from WS1 at Tyndall.....	19
Figure 9. Agenda for the impact workshop for researchers at Tyndall, 28 March 2023.....	20
Figure 10. Evaluation targets from WS2 at Tyndall.....	21
Figure 11. Agenda for the introductory workshop on CS for the CRG community, 8 May 2023	22
Figure 12. Evaluation targets from WS1 at CRG.....	23
Figure 13. Agenda for second workshop at CRG aimed at researchers and grants specialists, 8 May 2023..	24
Figure 14. Evaluation targets from WS2 at CRG.....	25
Figure 15. Agenda for workshop for researchers at UniSR, 19 May 2023	26
Figure 16. Evaluation targets from WS1 at UniSR.....	27
Figure 17. Agenda for workshop targeting research managers at UniSR, 19 May 2023	28
Figure 18. Evaluation target from WS2 at UniSR.....	29
Figure 19. Agenda for the Train-the-Trainer workshop at UniSR, 19 May 2023.....	30
Figure 20. Evaluation target from TTT at UniSR.....	31

List of Abbreviations

APRE	Agenzia per la promozione della ricerca europea, Coordinator
AU	Aarhus University, Front-Runner
CC-CS	Competence Center Citizen Science, Front-Runner
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation, Implementer
CS	Citizen science
ESF	Fondation Européen de la Science
FR	Front-Runner (some partners in TIME4CS: AU, CC-CS, UCL)
GA	Grounding Action
IA	Intervention Area
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology, Implementer
OS	Open Science
PES	Public Engagement in Science
RPOs	Research Performing Organisations
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
TTT	Train-the-Trainer
Tyndall	Tyndall National Institute, University College Cork, Implementer

UCL	University College London, Front-Runner
UniSR	Università Vita Salute San Raffaele, Implementer
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation

Executive Summary

The current document, titled 'Reports on all Workshops', has been developed within the framework of the TIME4CS project which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101006201.

The purpose of this Deliverable is to report on the training workshops developed and run under Task 4.2. This task stimulated organizational learning about Citizen Science (CS) skills and practices, their relations to Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and CS, and the importance of implementing the actions described in the roadmaps. In addition to the originally planned four Training Days at Implementer institutions, an additional workshop (Workshop 1: Train-the-Trainer) was requested by Implementers for the whole consortium, so all consortium partners could use the materials developed in Work Package (WP) 4 and run their own trainings based on the materials. The workshops and training days were as follows:

- Workshop 1: Train-the-Trainer workshop held during the TIME4CS General Assembly for all project partners, Brussels, 13 December 2022
- Training day 1: Workshops held at KTU, 13 March 2023
- Training day 2: Workshops held at Tyndall, 28 March 2023
- Training day 3: Workshops held at CRG, 8 May 2023
- Training day 4: Workshops held at UniSR, 19 May 2023

1. Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

The overall objective of WP4 is to build capacity within institutions for the use of responsible research and innovation (RRI), especially through citizen science (CS) and public engagement in science (PES). To better understand how to build this capacity through developing and conducting CS and PES (henceforth referred to as 'CS') training, T4.1 mapped existing CS courses, extracted relevant information, and developed training modules (described in D4.1). This report covers work done in relation to Task 4.2, i.e., the development and completion of workshops run for and at Implementer institutions.

Embedding CS in research performing organisations (RPOs) requires concerted effort and dedication, not only from a few dedicated researchers using CS as a method (bottom-up), but also from management and support functions within RPOs (top-down). These two approaches, bottom-up and top-down, are related to the two theoretical approaches TIME4CS builds on to effect institutional change, i.e., the social approach and the organisational approach, respectively. The social approach requires significant commitment of individuals to change their own behaviours, views, and mindsets, whereas the organisational approach focuses on modifying organisational structures, such as norms, procedures, and protocols¹.

With these two approaches and their involved individuals in mind, it becomes obvious that capacity building is required for researchers as well as management and other staff members. Hence workshops for each of these stakeholder groups were developed in collaboration with and held at each Implementer institution to target their particular staff members.

This deliverable reports on the numerous workshops run on four Training Days at Implementer institutions as well as the Train-the-Trainer workshop run as part of the TIME4CS General Assembly in December 2022. The report is structured in the following way: in Chapter 2, the development and planning aspects of the Training Days and workshops are explained. Chapter 3 describes the Trainings Days and workshops, including participants, approach, content, and reflections. Chapter 4 concludes the report and discusses lessons learned.

2. Development and planning of Training Days and workshops

2.1 Coordination with related activities

In the context of Task 3.3 “Mentoring Programme”, CC-CS was responsible for developing and executing mentoring visits, one visit hosted locally by each Implementer institution. Due to restrictions from the COVID-

¹ Dacin, M. T., Goodstein, J., & Scott, W. R. (2002). Institutional Theory and Institutional Change. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 45(1), 45–56. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3069284>

19 pandemic, the mentoring visits and training days had to be conducted within the same limited time frame, spring 2023. As the two activities targeted many of the same stakeholders, it was proposed to join the two visits. After careful consideration of stakeholders, budget, and time considerations by the consortium members, it was decided to merge the two activities. Implementer institutions therefore hosted 2-day TIME4CS activities, one day the mentoring visit, the other day the training workshops. This deliverable reports only on the training workshops held. Deliverable D3.3: Report on TIME4CS Mentoring Programme reports on the mentoring visits.

2.2 Overall preparation and development of workshops

The aim of the training day workshops was for AU, supported by the other FRs, to conduct relevant and targeted training workshops around the topics of the Grounding Actions (GA) each Implementer institution had chosen. Hence, preparation consisted of meeting individually with each Implementer institution to coordinate specific topics and cases, as well as discussing practicalities around numbers and backgrounds of participants, locations, and timings (more details under 3. Training Days and Workshops).

Workshops were developed specifically for each Implementer institution, though there were some overall considerations:

- Each workshop started with a brief introduction to the TIME4CS project, as not all participants knew much about the project
- Actual cases were presented from the Implementer institutions area of work where possible to make it as practically relevant as possible
- Powerpoint presentations were each kept to 20-25 min. for each topic with time afterwards for an interactive activity dealing with the topic presented
- Most presentations were given by AU, other FR partners (UCL and CC-CS) contributed. Representatives from FRs, APRE and ESF were present on all Training Days and provided support for participants during interactive sessions
- Interactive sessions, usually 20-30 min. each, were run as group activities where participants, supported by hand-outs related to the presentation, reflected on the topic within their own and their institution's contexts, making the discussions very focused and relevant for participants
- Training presentations were shared with Implementer institutions afterwards, to be further shared with workshop participants and other interested parties.

Each TIME4CS team at Implementer institutions handled the local planning and coordination, including:

- Promotion of workshops through targeted communications and proactive outreach to relevant stakeholders
- Participant registration, ensuring sharing of relevant details
- Logistics and catering, ensuring the smooth running of all workshops.

2.3 Documentation and Evaluation

The Train-the-Trainer workshop was evaluated by ZSI (WP5) using the ‘Human Scale’ (participants lining up according to their answers to a question) method.

The Training Day workshops, were evaluated using the ‘Target Evaluation’ method, suggested by ZSI (WP5) (example in Figure 1). At the end of each Training Day workshop, participants were asked to fill in a ‘Target’ featuring four questions related to the training they had just completed. For each question, they marked their agreement from 0% (outer circle) to 100% (inner circle/bullseye). Questions were different depending on the focus of the training workshops. For example, questions used for the WS1 for researchers at Tyndall were:

- I have a clear understanding of the communication and outreach activities required for a citizen science project
- I can explain what differentiates citizen science from other forms of participatory research
- I can evaluate for which type of research a citizen science approach would be beneficial
- I would like to connect more with the international citizen science community.

Figure 1. Target Evaluation. Example from UniSR workshop for Researchers, 19 May 2023.

3. Training Days and Workshops

The following subsections feature an overview and summary of each Training Day and all workshops held. This includes workshop participant types, particular considerations for the training approach taken (apart from aspects mentioned under 2.2 Overall preparation and development of workshops), learning goals and general observations. Training Day Agendas can be found in APPENDIX A.

3.1 Train-the-Trainer Workshop, Brussels, 13 December 2022

Train-the-Trainer (TTT) is a cascade methodology, aimed at equipping facilitators or trainers with the skills necessary to train others in the institution. Our TTT workshop was not initially planned in the project, but it was conducted due to requests from Implementer institutions. During discussions related to the sustainability of the developed training modules, it became apparent that Implementer institutions were uncertain about how to use the training modules after the project ends. Even though training workshops would be conducted as part of the project in spring 2023 at all Implementer institutions, the concern was that trainings related to GAs chosen later might be difficult to conduct. Therefore, it was decided that AU would run a 3.5-hour TTT workshop as part of the TIME4CS General Assembly in Brussels in December 2022. Representatives from all TIME4CS consortium partners participated in the workshop, though the focus was on Implementers, while the other partner organizations (Front-runners and impacts partners) assisted and encouraged the Implementers in their work.

The learning objectives of the TTT workshop were threefold (for agenda, see Figure 2):

- Conduct stakeholder and audience analyses for training design purposes
- Familiarise themselves with and use the TIME4CS Training Modules to design institutionally relevant training programs
- Plan and design customized training programs based on the available TMs and audience analysis in terms of learning objectives, content, activities, assessment, and intended outputs.

TIME4CS Train-the-Trainer (TTT) Overview

Time	Activities
9:30-10:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction, Purpose • Stakeholders & Audiences • <i>Interactive 1: Stakeholder Analysis – focus on Implementers</i> (open) • <i>IAs, GAs, Training Modules (TMs) Overview</i>
10:30-10:35	Break
10:35-11:35	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training Design • <i>Interactive 2: Design your own training</i> (in groups)
11:35-11:45	Break
11:45-12:50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wrap-up Interactive 2 • <i>Interactive 3: Identify challenges & solutions to implementing & embedding training & to 'next steps' – sustainability</i> • Plenum discussion • Next steps
12:50-13:00	Evaluation (ZSI)

Figure 2. Agenda for the Train-the-Trainer workshop for consortium members, Brussels, 13 Dec. 2023

The TTT workshop had three parts:

- The first session involved identifying stakeholders and potential audiences. AU introduced the basics of stakeholder analysis and Empathy Mapping, developed by Dave Gray, co-founder of strategy consultants Xplane. Empathy Mapping is a visualization technique used to gain insights into a target group or audience by reflecting on what they think or feel, hear and see, and say and do. The outcomes of the session were maps of stakeholders and audiences related to CS training at each Implementer institution.
- The second session revolved around the training modules described in deliverable D4.1. During the session, Implementers customized selected training modules for their audiences that were identified in the first session. AU introduced the Logic Model framework as a way to guide participants in their thinking about resources, activities, outputs, outcomes and eventual impacts of their training. All Implementers produced a Logic Model chart for up to two training modules.
- The third and final session was organised as a Fishbowl conversation between the Implementers. As a starting point for the discussion, all participants were asked to conduct a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis of the implementation and embedding of training programs at the implementing institutions. This included identification of institutional barriers to running the training programmes and making them sustainable. In the Fishbowl conversation,

representatives of implementing partners shared reflections on the training modules and ideas for the sustainability of CS training.

The TTT workshop was very successful as it made participants reflect on aspects of training they had not considered before, and it made them familiar with the training modules developed. It also gave Implementer institutions some ideas as to formats of trainings, making it easier for all to discuss and decide on best approach to workshops to be held at Implementer institutions during spring 2023.

3.2 Training Day KTU, 13 March 2023

3.2.1 WS1: Policy and Assessment Workshop

There were five participants in this workshop, apart from the KTU TIME4CS core team. All were management team members from different departments and very interested in the opportunities stemming from CS and in discussions of policy and researcher assessment related to CS (for agenda see Figure 3).

TIME4CS Policy and Assessment Workshop: Overview

Time	Activities
10:00-10:05	• About us and the TIME4CS project
10:05-10:25	• Strategic planning and research assessment for citizen science (M. Haklay)
10:25-10:45	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Perspectives, opportunities and challenges involved in making KTU a leading university in terms of citizen science and public participation in science (G. Kragh and K.H. Nielsen)
10:45-11:05	• Citizen science and societal impact: Developing an evaluation framework and communication strategy for citizen science projects (K.H. Nielsen)
11:05-11:25	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Research assessment criteria at KTU and opportunities for recognising citizen science and public participation in science efforts. Current and potential outreach practices (G. Kragh and K.H. Nielsen)
11:25-11:30	• Wrap-up and evaluation

Figure 3. Agenda for policy & assessment workshop at KTU, 13 March 2023

This workshop focused on strategic planning, research assessment, and public outreach. As there were only five participants, the interactive parts of the workshop were conducted as discussions among all participants and TIME4CS partners present. This allowed the management team members to also internally discuss and align on aspects of CS.

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Identify good examples of strategic adoption of CS
- Describe strategic goals for CS that are relevant to institutional policy-making
- Evaluate research assessment criteria that encompass the breadth of CS
- Discuss policy-making and funding opportunities for CS initiatives in national and international contexts

3.2.2 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 4), with some general observations:

- I can now name some good examples of how citizen science was strategically supported in other RPOs

Participants relatively highly agreed with this statement. This will hopefully provide a good basis and inspiration for further discussions at KTU regarding their including CS in their own strategies and policies.

- I have some concrete ideas how citizen science can be supported via institutional strategies and policies in my own institution

Most participants had low agreement with this statement. KTU policies and strategies were discussed in the interactive parts of the session, though it is a difficult topic to discuss in just 20 minutes. More time will be needed internally at KTU to discuss this topic more in-depth.

- I understand how research assessment criteria can consider the engagement in citizen science activities

Participants had a medium agreement with this statement, showing that participants had gotten some ideas in relation to including CS activities in researcher assessments, though more internal discussions will need to be had at KTU in relation to this.

- I have a clear understanding of the communication and outreach activities required for a citizen science project

Agreement with this statement was more varied around medium. We only covered it very briefly in the presentation and it was not the focus of most of the following discussion, but at least participants came away with some ideas for communication and outreach activities for CS projects.

All five participants evaluated the workshop.

Figure 4. Evaluation targets from WS1 at KTU.

3.2.3 WS2: Citizen Science Workshop

This workshop had been openly and widely advertised at KTU. The 12 participants came from different departments, e.g., chemistry and biology, and some were support staff while others were early career researchers and established researchers (for agenda see Figure 5).

TIME4CS Citizen Science Workshop: Overview

Time	Activities
13:30-13:35	• About us and the TIME4CS project
13:35-13:55	• Consideration for designing citizen science projects (M. Haklay)
13:55-14:15	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Identifying best types of citizen science and public participation in science for different KTU projects (G. Kragh and K.H. Nielsen)
14:15-14:35	• The international citizen science community and infrastructures (G. Kragh) • Communicating citizen science (K.H. Nielsen)
14:35-14:55	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Current and potential public outreach and citizen science communication and activities at KTU (G. Kragh and K.H. Nielsen)
14:55-15:00	• Wrap-up and evaluation

Figure 5. Agenda for second training workshop at KTU, 13 March 2023

This workshop was an introduction to CS and also considered communication aspects of projects and the possibility for international inspiration and cooperation. Most participants were completely new to CS, but the early career researchers were very interested in exploring how CS could become an integrated part of their projects. The communications staff also found the session on science communication useful in general.

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodologies
- Evaluate CS as an appropriate method for different types of research at KTU
- Discuss CS outreach and communication activities

3.2.3 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 6), with some general observations:

- I can explain what differentiates citizen science from other forms of participatory research

Most participants rated this statement highly, showing they had achieved a good idea of what CS is.

- I can evaluate for which type of research a citizen science approach would be beneficial

There was some variation in participants’ ratings of this statement, from medium to high, possibly reflecting their different backgrounds and roles.

- I would like to connect more with the international citizen science community

Here again a large spread of ratings from medium to high, most likely again reflecting the different backgrounds and roles of participants. Researchers expressed great interest in connecting with the international community, whereas communication staff might be more reluctant or less interested in doing so.

- I have a clear understanding of the communication and outreach activities required for a citizen science project

Participants were more confident with this statement, all rating it highly. We did spend quite a lot of time on the communication topic during the workshop which these ratings also suggest. With a number of communication staff attending, they would also have had some background knowledge in terms of potential communication and outreach activities that could be used for CS projects.

Eight (of 12) participants evaluated this workshop.

Figure 6. Evaluation targets from WS2 at KTU.

3.3 Training Day Tyndall, 28 March 2023

3.3.1 WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact

This workshop was attended by communication and engagement officers as well as researchers, in total 12 participants (for agenda see Figure 7).

TIME4CS Designing citizen science research for impact

Time	Activities
09:00-09:05	• About us and the TIME4CS project
09:05-09:25	• What is citizen science? What are the impacts of citizen science?
09:25-09:55	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Exploring connections between your research and citizen science methodologies
09:55-10:15	• How to find funding opportunities? How to design a citizen science proposal? What are the secrets to winning a grant?
10:15-10:45	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Matching your idea to the call Pitching your idea Writing the winning grant proposal
10:45-11:00	• Wrap-up and evaluation

Figure 7. Agenda for the impact and funding workshop at Tyndall, 28 March 2023

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodologies
- Evaluate CS as an appropriate method for different types of research at Tyndall
- Discuss and come up with ideas for funding opportunities for CS initiatives in national and international contexts

3.3.2 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 8), with some general observations:

- I can explain various citizen science methodologies and provide good examples

There was quite a spread in agreement to this statement, from low to high, possibly reflecting the participants' different roles in their organisation. However, the three participants giving low agreements to this question, also provided low agreement for all the other questions, raising the question whether they misunderstood the way the target evaluation worked and therefore potentially gave the opposite answers to what they meant.

- I can relate citizen science methodologies to my own research

This statement also received very varied agreement from low to high, most likely reflecting the participants' different roles. As at KTU, it is likely that engagement and communication officers rated this low as they are not conducting their own research, whereas researchers may rate it much higher.

- I have a clear understanding of how to design citizen science research for various types of impact

Participants rated their agreement with this statement only low to medium. This was potentially due to us only providing a very brief introduction to CS impacts, not the in-depth presentation that we used at other Implementer institution workshops.

- I have a clear understanding of how to scope the funding landscape for calls related to citizen science

Here again we saw the large spread of agreement from low to very high, again possibly reflecting the different roles of participants and with it different understandings and interest in the funding landscape and funding overall.

Only seven (of 12) participants evaluated the workshop, so the above is only a reflection of their responses.

Figure 8. Evaluation targets from WS1 at Tyndall.

3.3.3 WS2: Assessing the impacts of citizen science

Researchers at different levels as well as engagement and support officers participated in this second workshop, in total 14 participants (for agenda see Figure 9).

TIME4CS Assessing the impacts of citizen science

Time	Activities
11:30-11:45	• Measuring the impact of citizen science (MICS)
11:45-12:15	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Applying MICS indicators to your citizen science idea/project
12:15-12:30	• The international citizen science community and infrastructures • Communication in citizen science: A practical guide
12:30-12:55	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Developing communication activities for your citizen science idea/project
12:55-13:00	• Wrap-up and evaluation

Figure 9. Agenda for the impact workshop for researchers at Tyndall, 28 March 2023

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodologies
- Discuss how to measure the impact of CS
- Discuss CS outreach and communication activities

3.3.4 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 10), with some general observations:

- I can explain various citizen science methodologies and provide good examples

Participants rated their agreement with this statement as medium to high.

- I can relate citizen science methodologies to my own research

There was quite a spread in agreement to this statement, from very low to very high, most likely reflecting the participants' different roles. Communication staff would not be running their own research, so would probably rate it very low, whereas researchers would be able to directly relate it to their own research.

- I would like to connect more with the international citizen science community

Here again a large spread of ratings from medium to high, most likely again reflecting the different backgrounds and roles of participants. Researchers expressed great interest in connecting with the international community, whereas communication staff might be more reluctant to do so, similarly to our evaluation findings from KTU.

- I have a clear understanding of the communication and training activities that are relevant for citizen science

Participants rated this statement at medium to high level, suggesting that communication training is important both for communication and engagement staff but also for researchers.

Only five participants (of 14) evaluated the workshop, so the above only reflects their responses.

Figure 10. Evaluation targets from WS2 at Tyndall.

3.4 Training Day CRG, 8 May 2023

3.4.1 WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact

This first workshop was advertised to the whole CRG community and to other local biomedical research institutes (since the number of people registered was low) and eight people participated, seven of them from the CRG and one from an external research institute. CRG had requested a focus on the biomedical field to make the training more directly relatable for workshop participants (for agenda see Figure 11).

TIME4CS Designing citizen science research for impact

Time	Activities
10:00-10:05	• About us and the TIME4CS project
10:05-10:25	• What is citizen science?
10:25-10:50	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Exploring opportunities within your research using citizen science methodologies
10:50-11:10	• Measuring the impact of citizen science (MICS) • Communication in citizen science: A practical guide
11:10-11:40	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Applying MICS indicators to your citizen science idea/project Developing communication activities for your citizen science idea/project
11:40-11:55	• International outlook & Citizen Science for Health conference
11:55-12:00	• Wrap-up and evaluation

Figure 11. Agenda for the introductory workshop on CS for the CRG community, 8 May 2023

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodologies
- Evaluate CS as an appropriate method for different types of research at CRG
- Discuss how to measure the impact of CS
- Discuss CS outreach and communication activities

To accommodate the request of focusing on the (bio)medical field, we invited Sabine Wildevuur, the director of the DesignLab at University of Twente, a co-chair of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)'s Working Group on CS in Health and co-organiser of the upcoming CS for Health conference in October 2023, to talk about the international outlook for CS in the health sector as well as the upcoming conference.

3.4.2 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 12), with some general observations:

- I can explain various citizen science methodologies and provide good examples
Participants rated their agreement with this statement as medium-high.
- I can relate citizen science methodologies to the research conducted at my institution

Again, participants rated agreement with this statement as medium-high, possibly reflecting that current research at CRG is not based on CS, though they could see potential for integrating CS elements in current projects, or they had ideas for new projects that would use a CS approach.

- I would like to involve citizen science in health research proposals

General agreement with this statement was high, though one person rated it low. Potential funding avenues are generally of interest to researchers, so the high ratings were not a surprise as such, though it was good to see that they would consider integrating CS approaches in their future proposals.

- I have a clear understanding of how to include citizen science in relevant research proposals

Participants highly agreed with this statement, though again one person rated it very low.

Five (of eight) participants evaluated the workshop, so the above reflects their responses.

Figure 12. Evaluation targets from WS1 at CRG.

3.4.3 WS2: Citizen science in research project proposals

This second workshop was targeted at scientific project managers, grants specialists and principal investigators, and a total of 14 people participated (for agenda see Figure 13).

TIME4CS Citizen science in research project proposals

Time	Activities
14:00-14:05	• About us and the TIME4CS project
14:05-14:35	• What is citizen science? Citizen science for Health
14:35-14:50	• Stakeholder mapping in citizen science
14:50-15:10	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Stakeholder Analysis: who are influenced by and who can influence your research?
15:10-15:45	• How to find funding opportunities? How to design a citizen science proposal? What are the secrets to winning a grant? Where to find support at CRG? ➤ International & national funding
15:45-15:55	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Matching <u>your idea</u> to the <u>call</u> Pitching <u>your idea</u>
15:55-16:00	• Wrap-up and evaluation

 TIME4CS CS in research funding proposals, CRG, 8 May 2023

The TIME4CS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006201

Figure 13. Agenda for second workshop at CRG aimed at researchers and grants specialists, 8 May 2023

As we had no overview of national funding opportunities in Spain, two CRG Grants' specialists, provided an overview of national and local funding opportunities as part of the presentation.

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodology
- Conduct a stakeholder analysis for CS projects
- Discuss and come up with ideas for funding opportunities for CS initiatives in national and international contexts

3.4.4 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 14), with some general observations:

- I can explain various citizen science methodologies and provide good examples

Participants generally rated this statement highly and provided verbal feedback at the end of the workshop to the effect that they had appreciated all the (bio)medical cases we presented, making it easier for them to relate CS to their own research and institutional context.

- I can relate citizen science methodologies to my own research

This statement was rated medium to high by participants. This is likely a reflection of the roles of the participants, as some were not conducting their own research.

- I have a clear understanding of how to design citizen science research for various types of impact

There was quite a spread in agreement to this statement, from low to high, most likely reflecting participants' different roles within their institution. It could also be due to us focusing on the various types of impact, rather than the process of achieving the impacts.

- I have a clear understanding of how to scope the funding landscape for calls related to citizen science

Again, participants rated this statement very differently, from low to very high, most likely reflecting their different roles within CRG. Some were grants specialists and would have had a lot of knowledge of this topic already; others were researchers or project managers and would have had less experience with this topic.

Eleven (of 14) participants evaluated the workshop, so the above is only a reflection of their responses.

Figure 14. Evaluation targets from WS2 at CRG.

Both workshops helped raise awareness of CS among CRG staff, and they provided important opportunities to discuss possibilities and barriers to implementing CS at CRG.

3.5 Training Day UniSR, 19 May 2023

3.5.1 WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact

This workshop aimed at researchers was attended by 21 researchers of all levels: PhD students, junior and senior researchers as well as research group heads (for agenda see Figure 15).

TIME4CS Designing citizen science research for impact

Time	Activities
09:00-09:05	• About us and the TIME4CS project
09:05-09:25	• What is citizen science?
09:25-09:50	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Exploring opportunities within your research using citizen science methodologies
09:50-10:10	• Citizen Science for Health
10:10-10:20	• Measuring the impact of citizen science (MICS)
10:20-10:40	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Applying MICS indicators to your citizen science idea/project
10:40-10:55	• Chiara Di Resta: Uni4Me
10:55-11:00	• Wrap-up and evaluation

Figure 15. Agenda for workshop for researchers at UniSR, 19 May 2023

We gave a brief overview of the CS in health area and mentioned the upcoming CS for Health conference in October 2023. When the call for abstracts closed (June 18th), we were advised that a number of abstracts had been submitted from UniSR. Finally, a UniSR researcher presented her own UniSR CS project called Uni4Me, providing participants with a great example of CS already happening at UniSR.

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodologies
- Evaluate CS as an appropriate method for different types of research at UniSR
- Discuss how to measure the impact of CS
- Discuss current CS projects at UniSR

3.5.2 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 16), with some general observations:

- I can explain various citizen science methodologies and provide good examples

Agreement with this statement from participants ranged from medium to very high. Like at CRG, here at UniSR we presented a range of health-related CS cases, possibly making it easier for participants to relate CS to their own research.

- I can relate citizen science methodologies to my own research

Again, participants agreed with this statement on a medium to very high level. This also reflected the deep discussions in the interactive session around this topic where participants got really engaged.

- I understand how research impact criteria can include the engagement in citizen science activities

Also for this statement, participants agreed at a level of medium to very high which also reflected that they had time during the interactive session to discuss impacts of CS projects.

- I would like to connect more with the international citizen science community

Most participants would like to connect more with the international CS community, something it is now possible for them to do as UniSR has become a member of the European Citizen Science Association and chair of a working group (WG) on CS in Universities. We also presented other opportunities and WGs to give some ideas of how to further engage internationally.

Fifteen (of 21) participants evaluated the workshop, so the above is only a reflection of their responses.

Figure 16. Evaluation targets from WS1 at UniSR.

3.5.3 WS2: Citizen Science Methodologies & Communication

This workshop targeted research managers and supporting staff and nine people participated, in addition to the eight members of the core UniSR TIME4CS team (for agenda see Figure 17).

TIME4CS Citizen Science Methodologies & Communication

Time	Activities
11:30-11:35	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> About us and the TIME4CS project
11:35-11:50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is citizen science? Communication is critical in citizen science
11:50-12:10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Interactive session:</i> Exploring opportunities within UniSR for using citizen science methodologies Developing communication activities for citizen science projects
12:10-12:20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What universities need to change for public engagement and citizen science
12:20-12:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Q&A Wrap-up & evaluation

Figure 17. Agenda for workshop targeting research managers at UniSR, 19 May 2023

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Describe CS methodologies
- Evaluate CS as an appropriate method for different types of research at UniSR
- Discuss CS outreach and communication activities

3.5.4 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 18), with some general observations:

- I can explain what differentiates citizen science from other forms of participatory research

Participants agreed highly with this statement, also reflecting their keen interest and potentially some prior knowledge of CS.

- I can evaluate for which type of research a citizen science approach would be beneficial

Participants also agreed highly with this statement, highlighting the usefulness of providing very specific CS cases from within the participants' own research area(s).

- I think that my organisation should continue to support citizen science

All very highly agreed with this statement, showing how important the TIME4CS project and the hard work put in by the UniSR core team have been in raising awareness and support for CS within UniSR. This has then also created the expectation from researchers, that UniSR will continue to support CS initiatives even after the TIME4CS project ends.

- I have a clear understanding of the communication and outreach activities required for a citizen science project

Participant agreement with this statement ranged from medium to very high, possibly reflecting the time constraint during the one interactive session to discuss both opportunities within UniSR as well as communication aspects. This also highlighted our reflection that two hours is the minimum time for a workshop to allow for two interactive sessions and more in-depth discussions.

Five (of nine) participants evaluated the workshop, so the above is only a reflection of their responses.

Figure 18. Evaluation target from WS2 at UniSR.

3.5.5 WS3: Train-the-Trainer

This workshop was aimed at the eight members of the UniSR TIME4CS core team who all participated (for agenda see Figure 19).

TIME4CS Train-the-Trainer (TTT) Overview

Time	Activities
14:00-14:05	• Introduction
14:05-14:20	• Stakeholders & Audiences
14:20-14:45	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Stakeholder analysis
14:45-15:00	• Training Design
15:00-15:25	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Design your own training
15:25-15:35	• Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats (SWOT)
15:35-15:55	• <i>Interactive session:</i> Identify challenges & solutions to implementing & embedding training & to 'next steps'
15:55-16:00	• Wrap up and evaluation

The TIME4CS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006201

Figure 19. Agenda for the Train-the-Trainer workshop at UniSR, 19 May 2023

Learning objectives of this workshop were for participants to be able to:

- Conduct stakeholder and audience analyses for training design purposes
- Plan and design customized training programs and audience analysis in terms of learning objectives, content, activities, assessment, and intended outputs.
- Conduct a SWOT analysis, identifying challenges and solutions within their own contexts for implementing CS trainings.

3.5.6 Evaluation and general observations

The evaluation questions for this workshop were the following (Figure 20), with some general observations:

All statements were agreed to at high or very high levels, reflecting also how the UniSR core team have been working with CS for a long time now and have a very good understanding of different aspects of CS.

- I have an understanding of the stakeholders involved in citizen science

One of the interactive sessions provided an opportunity for participants to reflect on stakeholders and potential training audiences, seemingly a very useful exercise for participants to expand their understanding of both CS and aspects of providing training for potential CS researchers and other staff.

- I have some concrete ideas how citizen science can be supported via support resources and infrastructures in my own organisation

As already mentioned, the UniSR core team have been working actively with their chosen Grounding Actions in the TIME4CS project and therefore have a very good understanding of what is required to support and embed CS in their institution.

- I feel confident in performing a stakeholder mapping for citizen science at my institution

The UniSR core team will most likely be discussing stakeholders in CS projects with researchers going forward, so this very high rating of confidence in performing stakeholder mapping is a great starting point and will be important in their future work.

- I have a clear understanding of how to design training modules that support citizen science activities at my institution

Another great rating by the core team members that instils confidence in their ability to run great training activities for all at UniSR.

Only three (of eight) participants evaluated the workshop, so the above reflects only their responses.

Figure 20. Evaluation target from TTT at UniSR.

4. Conclusions

This deliverable reports on the Training Days and workshops run for the whole consortium and at each of the Implementer institutions during December 2022 and spring 2023 under Task 4.2.

Our evaluations provided a wealth of information and ideas for improvements which we implemented in subsequent workshops, when possible, which we believe is also reflected in the highest agreements with our evaluation statements during our last workshops. Lessons learned from running these workshops include:

- Each workshop needs to start with a general introduction to CS, as participants have very different ideas of what CS is. Therefore, starting everyone off with an overview provides a basis for all subsequent discussions
- Providing practical case studies from within workshop participants' own research fields is very important, making it easier for people to relate concepts and ideas to their own research context
- Interactive sessions worked very well and helped make the workshops more relevant and bring the topics closer to the practical realities of the participants. Twenty minutes should be the minimum for these types of sessions to allow discussions to progress meaningfully
- If conducting trainings for mixed audiences, e.g., communication staff and researchers, within the same workshop, it can be challenging to make the content relevant to all participants. Their roles are very different, both within their institutions, but also within potential CS projects. Therefore, as far as possible, target audiences for future workshops should ideally have similar roles within the institution, e.g., all researchers, or all support, communication, or engagement officers.
- Workshops should be a minimum of two hours to allow for meaningful interactive sessions for participants

APPENDIX A

A.1 KTU Training Day

A.1.1 Training Day Agenda

Time	Activity
9:30 - 9:45	Arrival (coffee)
10:00 – 11:30	WS1: Policy and assessment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Why is CS important for the institution? Intervention area “Policy & Assessment”: Impact of CS
11:45 – 13:00	Lunch
13:30 – 15:00	WS2: Introduction to citizen science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intervention areas “Research” & “Education & Awareness” Good practice cases of CS use, engagement tools, communication

Table 1. Agenda for Training Day visit to KTU, 13 March 2023

A.2 Tyndall Training Day

A.2.1 Training Day Agenda

Time	Activity
9.00-11.00	WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to citizen science Funding opportunities and proposal writing
11.00-11.30	Break
11.30-13.00	WS2: Assessing the impacts of citizen science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measuring impact of citizen science Communication in citizen science

Table 2. Agenda for Training Day visit to Tyndall, 28 March 2023

A.3 CRG Training Day

A.3.1 Training Day Agenda

Time	Activity
9:30 - 10:00	Arrival & coffee
10:00 – 12:00	WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of citizen science methodologies Discuss ideas for citizen science projects
12:00 – 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 16:00	WS2: Citizen science in research project proposals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of citizen science methodologies, impact and stakeholders Discuss funding bodies and calls that include, or could include, citizen science research activities Plan or envisage current or new research projects using citizen science

Table 3. Agenda for Training Day visit to CRG, 8 May 2023

A.4 UniSR Training Day

A.4.1 Training Day Agenda

Time	Activity
8.45-9.00	Welcome
9.00-11.00	WS1: Designing citizen science research for impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop for researchers on Citizen Science Focus on Citizen Science for UniSR and OSR research communities with practical examples and concrete case studies on biomedicine & philosophy
11.00-11.30	Break
11.30-12.30	WS2: Citizen science methodologies & communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop for managers and supporting offices Provide concrete examples to research managers and supporting staff to ease the identification of Citizen Science initiatives
12.30-14.00	Lunch
14.00-16.00	WS3: Train-the-trainers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Targeted at the UniSR project core team Training design, stakeholder analysis, challenges & potential solutions
	Final remarks and close

Table 4. Agenda for Training Day visit to UniSR, 19 May 2023